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The value of nature in EU policy: Discursive tendencies before and after the Green Deal

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Executive summary

This report analyses how the EU employs different kinds of valuations of nature by examining discursive tendencies related to these valuations in selected EU policy documents from before, during and after the Green Deal. It aims to present and discuss discursive changes over time concerning the value of nature. To this end, twelve EU policy documents are examined with regard to these tendencies, to understand which values of nature are not only recognised but also supported by environmental policy, and which are neglected or discursively subordinated.

Academic scholarship often builds on discourse analysis of environmental policy in order to lay bare existing power structures and representations of nature in policy, to reveal underlying valuations or normative assumptions, and thus indicate potential effects on wider social practice. This report builds on this literature and contributes to it by explicitly uncovering how different values of nature are represented in environmental policy discourse. Our analysis builds on a widely-accepted distinction of values in the debate on environmental policy, between *instrumental value* (something valued as a substitutable means to a human end), *intrinsic value* (something valuable in and of itself), and *relational value* (a non-substitutable, meaningful relationship between people and nature). Our report aligns relevant discursive tendencies with these three value types.

The report presents a conceptual framework that was iteratively built based on discursive tendencies found throughout the documents. We briefly analyse the

selected documents and then present an overall analysis of the diachronic discursive changes comparing phases before, during and after the Deal. The key findings are as follows:

- Each document comprises several tendencies, but always to varying degrees and with different grades of emphasis.
- While intrinsic value serves as a primary rationale in earlier environmental policy, it is increasingly embedded within and subordinated to instrumental framings in post-Green Deal regulation.
- On the one hand, embedding environmental policy within broader strategies such as the Green Deal enhances its political salience overall and increases its reach to other EU policy domains.
- On the other hand, the Green Deal appears to restructure the hierarchy of values, making environmental protection contingent upon its contribution to economic prosperity, or resilience, which is evidence for its subordination to broader instrumental framings.
- However, the analysis shows that this trend of subordination to instrumental valuation tendencies predates the Green Deal.
- Finally, the emergence of a geopolitical asset framing in the post-Green Deal phase marks a further development of this trajectory and only shows an intensification of instrumentalisation.

Introduction

This report was prepared in March and April 2026 by SAEGE. It contributes to the EGE's forthcoming Opinion on the value of nature, as requested by the European Commission. It presents material developed by SAEGE in response to a second Specification of Work, following a previous Specification of Work which led to two reports (SAEGE 2026a, SAEGE 2026b). These two earlier reports, combined with the present report, form a single workflow supporting the EGE's reflection on this topic. The European Commission requested advice from the EGE on approaches to valuing nature in governance and across society, particularly in relation to the ethical questions that emerge from how humans relate to nature and their responsibility towards it. The questions posed by the European Commission to the EGE were as follows:

- Which assumptions about the value of nature, biodiversity, ecosystems and of the relationship of humans to nature should underpin policy decisions? How are these dimensions integrated into (economic) policymaking at EU and national levels, and in underlying models used for impact assessment, policy design, monitoring and evaluation? On this basis, what kinds of governance action are required, also with regard to the further development of the European Green Deal and of what is to follow it, and the EU's strategies and actions in the global context?
- What are important ethical considerations as regards conceptualisations about the rights and standing of non-human parts of nature? Who is best placed to invoke, enshrine, and adjudicate these rights — and on what basis?

- How are approaches that value nature, and human actions with effect on nature, in economic terms to be assessed from an ethical perspective? What are important ethical perspectives as regards socioeconomic systems and the need for a global transition to sustainability?

The EU employs numerous framings with regards to the value of nature, especially in environmental policy documents. These framings have developed over time and can be encapsulated by common discursive tendencies concerning the value of nature. Further, the Green Deal is viewed as an important shift in environmental policy of the EU. This report therefore examines relevant discursive tendencies in selected EU environmental policy documents and how they developed from before the Green Deal phase, during this phase and towards the post-Green Deal phase. The analysis works by means of a critical hermeneutic discourse analysis aiming to reveal how the European Union frames the value of nature in the documents selected and how these framings have evolved over time, thus supporting the EGE's ethical reflection on the value of nature in EU policy.

The report first presents the methodological foundation for the critical hermeneutic discourse analysis. We introduce the selected documents in chronological order and — in part building on our two earlier reports on the value of nature — we then elaborate the conceptual framework to identify relevant discursive tendencies. Second, in the 'Analysis and results' section, we analyse each document, employing the conceptual framework; the discursive changes throughout the phases are made explicit. Finally, in a concluding 'Discussion' section, we lay out major findings from this overall analysis.

Methods

1. Discourse analysis and environmental policy

The aim of our critical hermeneutic discourse analysis is to reveal how the European Union frames the value of nature in selected policy and policy communication documents and how these framings have evolved over time. The analysis spans key phases of EU environmental policymaking, including the period preceding the European Green Deal, the implementation phase of the Green Deal itself, and its subsequent aftermath.

Discourse analytical tools in general are particularly fitting for the field of environmental policy-making for several reasons. First, as Schunz (2022) and Leipold et al. (2019) argue, a central assumption of critical discourse analysis is that discursive practices ultimately shape action. These actions extend beyond the discursive sphere and have material consequences for social arrangements. This assumption is especially relevant when applying discourse analysis to policy, as EU regulations have far-reaching effects on societies across the Union. Moreover, this policy area is highly contested, with various actors frequently responding to one another's claims and statements, often in rapid succession. Finally, it is agreed in the academic debate on discourse analysis that this method enables to reveal underlying assumptions, judgements and values (e.g. Stevenson 2019) which makes this particularly relevant for ethical policy advice. Over the past decades, the EU has introduced and adopted numerous major environmental regulations while also integrating environmental considerations into an expanding set of policy domains. Some scholars, such as Schunz (2022), characterise the Green Deal as a major paradigm shift in this regard. Schunz

states that the "EU has regularly adopted long-term discursive frames via multi-annual political strategies: the EGD 'supersede[s]' the 2000 'Lisbon Strategy' (LS) and the 2010 'Europe 2020' (E2020) strategy" (p.2) and that "EU policy-makers must systematically frame individual initiatives within the overarching narrative" (p.4). This further justifies structuring our analysis around the three periods before, during and after the Green Deal.

In order to identify discursive trends in EU environmental policy, we here employ a critical hermeneutic discourse analysis methodology. After selecting policy documents for each period, both authors first read and analysed the documents, marking relevant passages containing phrases that refer to explicit or implicit assumptions on the value of nature. Tables, graphs, glossaries and annexes were deemed unsuitable and excluded from the analysis. Both authors cross-checked each other's marked passages, signalling terms and first analyses. From these marked passages and signalling terms, we generated initial discursive tendencies and iteratively built a conceptual framework presenting the discursive tendencies overall.

After completing the initial analysis of all documents, we then reviewed and refined these discursive tendencies and cross-checked the findings with the discourses uncovered by other academic scholarship to understand whether we were missing important ones (e.g. Leipold et al., 2019). Finally, we used the signalling terms to identify discursive tendencies in all of the selected documents. Whenever signalling terms appeared in the documents, we checked the context of the sentence to understand whether these did in fact point to a discursive tendency (for instance, mentioning economic terminology does not always reflect instrumental discursive tendencies).

The discursive tendencies were in the end conceptually linked to specific values of nature (instrumental, intrinsic, relational). In our analysis, we thus moved from signalling terms to discursive tendencies, and then to valuation types. Employing these types of values of nature is thus not neutral, but presupposes the tripartite categorisation following Christie et al. (2021) and Chan et al. (2016). Although this categorisation is not absolute (values show overlaps and conflict at times), Himes et al. (2024) argue that maintaining a working distinction between instrumental and relational domains remains important for effective environmental policy implementation and we assume that this distinction may equally matter for ethical reflection on relevant policy options. The conceptual framework used for our analysis is described and elaborated in section 3 below.

The method we employed builds on commonly-used discourse analysis methods in academic literature on environmental policy (Froese and Loft, 2025; Schunz, 2022; Leipold et al., 2019). As Leipold et al. (2019) argue, “discourse analysis encompasses a broader field of related approaches that can be grouped, inter alia, into those that emphasise the study of either language use or of socio-cultural meaning structures” (p. 447). Building on this distinction, we follow their suggestion that discourse analysis in environmental policy primarily engages with these underlying meaning structures. To this end, we identify broader discursive tendencies that go beyond explicit language use and are interpretative in nature. We follow Froese and Loft (2025) in recognising that policy documents need not contain explicit statements of valuation to convey them. Rather, such documents articulate and privilege certain approaches, and “marginalise alternative approaches through discursive framing” (p. 3). Accordingly, our analysis places particular emphasis on identifying terms and formulations that (may) convey valuations of nature. This includes not only explicit expressions, but also implicit language, seemingly neutral phrasing, and even the absence of specific references to nature’s value where such omissions may be meaningful. In contrast to Froese and Loft, we

did not use a codified or otherwise automated search and analysis method but relied on these broad, interpretative and selective views on the value of nature, which also include both evaluative and normative assumptions or framings. This in turn explains why we opted for a “critical hermeneutic” discourse analysis. Since we intended for the underlying normative assumption regarding the value of nature to be revealed by the analysis, we employed interpretative stances and methods.

Finally, our method generally involves a two-tiered approach: First, we analysed the selected documents individually with regard to the major discursive trends and second, we took a diachronic stance in order to determine how the EU’s framings have evolved over time. This puts a special emphasis on developments, additions and major shifts occurring overall and between the periods represented by the documents selected.

2. Selection of policy documents

The selection of policy documents was guided by three main criteria:

- EU policy documents included in the analysis are identified as relevant environmental policies in the EGE policy landscape document.
- Although EU environmental policy does not exhibit clearly demarcated phases, the documents can be considered broadly representative of three periods: the pre-Green Deal phase, the Green Deal era, and the

post-Green Deal period.¹ These are not clear-cut phases, since they overlap and the policy from these phases also builds on each other. However, it is heuristically useful to distinguish these phases in order to understand how the Green Deal can be a point of reference in relation to which discursive shifts can be discerned.

- For each policy, we identified the corresponding documents available on EUR-Lex. The analysis also draws on policy communication documents for the following documents: Biodiversity Strategy, Omnibus: Simplifying for sustainable competitiveness, Common Agricultural Policy 2023–2027, Clean Industrial Deal, Nature Credits Roadmap, EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, and the European Green Deal. As the Common Agricultural Policy 2023–2027 lays out ten specific objectives, we selected two relevant objectives for our analysis as well as the document that summarises the objectives.

This selection further entails several limitations:

- The number of policies analysed is relatively small, but as the selected cases represent major environmental policies, they provide sufficient material to support meaningful analysis and allow representative findings in this respect. For example, the Birds and Habitats Directives are described as the “backbone” of EU environmental policy (European Commission, n.d.), upon which many subsequent initiatives build.
- The analysis focuses exclusively on policy and policy communication documents, confining the findings to institutionalised forms of discourse. Discourse-analytical research in environmental policy

frequently incorporates additional sources, such as political speeches (e.g., Schunz, 2022), thereby enabling a more comprehensive account of the discourse. To mitigate this limitation, our findings are cross-checked against existing academic literature (e.g., Leipold et al., 2019) to ensure that key discursive patterns are not overlooked.

- While some of the strategy documents analysed here (e.g. the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030) do contain relatively concrete policy targets and reference to more downstream regulation, our analysis also contrasts with approaches that integrate both discourse and wider social practice (e.g., Behagel et al., 2019).
- The temporal interpretation of discursive shifts requires careful qualification. The absence of a particular framing of nature’s value (e.g. intrinsic value) in later phases of policymaking does not necessarily indicate that such valuations have lost relevance. Rather, they may have been institutionalised in earlier policy frameworks that continue to apply, including through amendments or updated versions (e.g. the Birds Directive). Conversely, the emergence of new framings constitutes a significant discursive development (e.g. the multitude of economic framings of nature in later phases) and represents a meaningful finding of this analysis.

We here follow an ordering of the selected documents according to which there are three major periods to analyse and to then compare with regard to discursive shifts. The ordering is summarised in the table overleaf.

¹ Schunz (2022) offers a slightly different distinction of three phases for his analysis of the Green Deal as a paradigm shift in discourses on sustainability. He divides the timeline into phases from the Lisbon Treaty (2000s), the ‘European strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth’ (2010-2020) and the Green Deal (first half of 2020s). However, in this report, we incorporate documents

from the pre-Green Deal phase (1980s to 2019), the Green Deal era (2019-2023) and the post-Green Deal phase (2023-2026).

Table 1. Policy documents selection and phases

Phase	Policy document	Year
Pre-Green Deal (ca. 1979–2019)	Birds Directive	1979; codified 2009
	Habitats Directive	1992
	Water Framework Directive	2000
	Environmental Liability Directive	2004; amended 2019
Green Deal era (ca. 2019–2023)	European Green Deal	2019
	EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030	2020
	The new Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027: CAP Objective 4: Agriculture and climate mitigation (2019) CAP Objective 6: Biodiversity and farmed landscapes (2019) CAP Summary of CAP Strategic Plans for 2023-2027: joint effort and collective ambition (2023)	2019–2023
	EU Climate Adaptation Strategy	2021
	Nature Restoration and amending Regulation	2024
	Clean Industrial Deal	2025
Post-Green Deal (ca. 2023–2026)	Nature Credits Roadmap	2025
	Omnibus: Simplifying for sustainable competitiveness	2025

3. Conceptual framework

The analysis of these policy documents is based on a conceptual framework comprising of signalling terms, allocated to specific discourse tendencies, which may in turn be specified regarding the value type they represent for nature. The table overleaf thus provides a breakdown concerning the value types (column 1), the major discursive tendencies (column 2) and relevant signalling terms (column 3). This framework has the benefit of both representing important valuations of nature in the EU policy documents selected and reflecting major discourses on nature more generally. It has the limitations of not necessarily being comprehensive, since there may be further discourses which draw on nature and the environment as well as classifying these tendencies rather strictly with regards to a tripartite value typology which does not directly make any conflicts or overlaps between these types visible. However, this enables an analysis which is foundational for ethical policy advice, since normative and evaluative assumptions in the policy documents are made explicit and accessible through common discursive tendencies and value types which are often considered to represent distinct categories.

Major discursive tendency	Description	Signalling terms
Intrinsic values		
Conservation	In this tendency, nature is framed as something worth protecting and conserving. This tendency assigns intrinsic value to environmental features, wild or largely inviolate, intact ecosystems and species, thus arguing for non-intervention by humans.	protection prevention / prevent conservation long-term survival wild loss species/natural entities are under pressure / threat species should survive / thrive
Normative limits	In this tendency, nature is understood as in need of protection from (especially human) disturbance and as protectable through legal boundaries. By pointing towards measures against commodification, exploitation, or degradation, this discourse frames nature as intrinsically valuable. On a scale of strictness, it may formulate legal sanctions.	non-commercialisation / non-commodification of nature maintaining environmental safeguards precaution / prohibition / non-negotiable / non-acceptance of environmental degradation/ destruction/ harm /disturbance / exploitation / pollution of ecosystems / extinction of species
Ecological integrity	This tendency attributes intrinsic value to the ecological balance or integrity of ecosystems, environmental features or species. The integrity or 'wholeness of such are here viewed as valuable independently from humans.	coherent whole biological balance integrity of sites complexity of ecosystems
Instrumental values		
Economic asset	In this tendency, nature is first and foremost a resource in service of humans. This may be signaled by a range of ecosystem services, costs and capital assigned to nature and environmental harms framing nature in economic terms generally.	ecosystem services nature credits natural capital carbon stocks and sinks costs / proportional costs / expense reducing environmental costs polluter pays principle damage to the economy economic dependencies on nature disproportionate costs of environmental remediation / restoration securing water supply supply and demand blue economy nature as something that can be registered, pooled, banked and transacted
Green growth	This tendency sees the potential to decouple innovation and economic growth from environmental harm. Nature is here instrumentally valuable since natural goods, sustainability, or renewable energy are viewed as means to economic prosperity or	decoupling economic growth from natural resource use bioeconomy jobs competitiveness decarbonisation

Major discursive tendency	Description	Signalling terms
	competitiveness. According to this discourse nature is not an obstacle but an ally in achieving economic growth.	circularity / circular economy sustainable path sustainable development green transition new growth strategy prosperity competitiveness economic and environmental objectives in tandem
Technosolutionism or ecomodernism	In this tendency, nature is viewed as a quasi-technological domain that can be repaired, restored and improved, and technologies are framed as solution strategies to manage, control or manipulate nature or to fix environmental damages. Nature according to this is manageable or moldable and it is instrumentally valuable, as innovation, technologies and economic efficiency should be served by nature.	new technologies / sustainable solutions / disruptive innovation clean technology repair restore recover return to baseline clean up remedy improve enhance control manage / management sustainable solutions (increase) efficiency adaptation mitigation mitigation technologies
Risks	Here, nature is associated with risks, and it is framed with regard to the potential harms it may cause to humans like climate change or pandemics. Dealing with these risks is considered to be of great instrumental value to humans.	climate risks natural/environmental threats (e.g. pandemics) threat multiplier source of instability significant damage to human health nature as an insurance policy hedge against risks boosting resilience / preventing environmental risks e.g. pandemics
Geopolitical asset	According to this tendency, nature is increasingly valuable in instrumental terms in order to achieve political ends like resilience, strategic autonomy and independence. Features of the environment are framed here as serving geopolitical strategies.	strategic autonomy security availability of natural resources resilience tied to security or strategy maintaining resource resilience / resource security dependence on import of natural resources

Major discursive tendency	Description	Signalling terms
Relational values		
Responsibility or stewardship	In this tendency, the care for natural environments or species is motivated by a concern for the heritage found in nature, as well as a concern for present and future generations. The responsible and sustainable use of natural resources is part of a relational value with nature here.	heritage care long-term responsibility maintenance extensive agriculture stewards future generations
Participation	According to this tendency, humans should be enabled to participate in interactions with natural environments or decision-making related to care and stewardship for nature. This type of involvement is seen as a feature of a relational value of nature.	just transition stakeholder engagement cross-society participation civil society indigenous peoples and local communities
Interdependence	In this tendency, the mutual dependence of humans and non-human-nature is stressed and framed in terms of approaches to health and measures to enable co-living of humans with nature. This is viewed as a relational value.	recognising interdependence urban greening / urban green space dependence of human well-being on the environment one health approach

Table 2. Conceptual framework

Analysis and results

1. Analysis of each policy document

Each item from our selection of documents is analysed below, aiming to reveal discursive tendencies in the policy documents, employing the conceptual framework introduced above. Discursive tendencies are in *italics*.

Pre-Green Deal

Birds Directive (1979)

This Directive was established to protect wild bird species in the EU as well as their habitats. It is the oldest piece of EU legislation on the environment and forms the cornerstone of EU biodiversity policy, together with the Habitats Directive. This Directive constructs the value of nature predominantly through a *conservation* discursive tendency, in which nature is framed as requiring protection. Central signalling terms such as “conservation”, “protection”, “preservation”, “maintenance”, and “restoration” recur throughout the document and reflect a strong intrinsic valuation of nature, emphasising the survival and ecological integrity of bird species and habitats. It emphasises *ecological integrity of the natural environment*, with phrasings like “coherent whole” (p. 1). The articulation of *normative limits*, particularly through prohibitive language such as “ban”, “prohibit”, and “avoid deterioration”, establishes clear boundaries against exploitation and environmental harm (pp. 2–3). At the same time, this intrinsic framing is complemented by elements of an anthropocentric instrumental valuation framing, particularly where nature is described as a “natural resource” that can be managed and controlled (p. 1), indicating an

ecomodernist discursive tendency. Secondary to the dominant *conservation* discourse appears a discursive tendency pointing to a relational valuation, as introduced in the framing of birds as part of a shared European “heritage”, entailing a common *responsibility* (p. 1). Overall, the most dominant discursive tendency is *conservation*, and the prevailing value type is intrinsic, albeit embedded with a managerial tone.

Habitats Directive (1992)

The Habitats Directive mainly aims at protecting biodiversity across Member States, under a special European network of conservation named the Natura 2000 network. The Directive complements the Birds Directive by providing protection for a range of plants, animals (other than birds) and habitats which are considered to be of particular importance. The Directive exhibits a predominantly discursive tendency of *conservation*, in which nature is framed as requiring protection independent of explicit human utility. Signalling terms such as “conservation” and “protection” appear often, construing nature as an entity with intrinsic value. Habitats are seen as requiring urgent, collective protection and maintenance. The policy foregrounds long-term survival and ecological continuity (p. 4) signalling the *ecological integrity* discursive tendency. It also lists *normative limits*, expressed in language such as the obligation to avoid “deterioration of natural habitats” and “disturbance of species” (p. 6), indicating non-negotiable ecological thresholds. The framing of habitats and species as part of the Community’s “natural heritage” (p. 2) and their conservation as a responsibility of the Community (p. 3) introduces a relational feature. Instrumental framings are present but subordinated, typically embedded in references to “sustainable development” (p. 2) and “economic,

social and cultural requirements” (p. 2). Overall, the dominant value type is intrinsic, with a strong emphasis on *ecological integrity* (e.g. “coherent European ecological network”; p. 2) and system-level functioning.

Water Framework Directive (2004)

The Water Framework Directive aims to establish a framework for the protection of all EU water bodies. It exhibits a strong *conservation* discursive tendency, as among its purposes is a framework which “ensures the progressive reduction of pollution of groundwater and prevents its further pollution” (p. 5) and which “prevents further deterioration and protects and enhances the status of aquatic ecosystem” (p. 5). Also, “good surface water status” in Member States (p. 9) is an environmental objective of the Directive. In particular, the signalling term “prevent” is used numerous times throughout the regulation. From the outset, the Directive excludes water from being a “commercial product” (p. 1), signalling its intrinsic value. These and other features highlight the protection, maintenance, and long-term *ecological integrity* of water bodies, often framing them as needing protection in their own right. Hence, the nature *conservation* discourse underlying intrinsic valuation is here dominant. Further, it establishes *normative limits* to harm and exploitation, requiring Member States to “implement the necessary measures to prevent deterioration of the status of all bodies of surface water” (p. 9), to establish “environmental quality standards” (e.g. p. 18), and to impose penalties to deter harmful human influence (p. 20). Here, the regulation uses phrasings that signal the prohibition of emissions, restriction of pollution of groundwater bodies and the maintaining of safeguards when it comes to protected areas. Thus, the *normative limits* for nature discursive tendency appears also dominant. With regard to a more instrumental value of nature discursive tendencies, the Directive explicitly mentions the “polluter pays principle” (p. 12-13), a principle mainly in place to allocate responsibilities for harms caused to services from ecosystems. It employs a pricing of natural goods by pointing towards a “recovery of the costs of water services” (p. 13) and it potentially allows trade-offs between intrinsic

and instrumental values of water as measures may be relaxed if achieving objectives is “disproportionately expensive” (p. 10). All of these are part of the *economic asset* discursive tendency. This becomes further evident through this definition used throughout the Directive: “Water services’ means all services which provide, for households, public institutions or any economic activity” (p. 7). Overall, some intrinsic and instrumental tendencies are dominant in this document.

Environmental Liability Directive (2004, amended 2019)

The Environmental Liability Directive aims at establishing a comprehensive EU-wide liability regime for environmental damage. It exhibits a predominantly instrumental framing of nature, structured around a *technosolutionist* framing of damage, restoration, and liability. It starts off with an *economic asset* discursive tendency, outlining the polluter-pays principle (p. 2) that reinforces an economic rationality in which environmental harm is internalised as a cost. Throughout the Directive, nature is consistently articulated as a system of functions and services that can be impaired, measured, and restored to a “baseline condition”, (p. 2) rather than as an entity with intrinsic worth. This is evident in the definition of damage as a “measurable adverse change in a natural resource or measurable impairment of a natural resource service” (p. 4), and in the emphasis on restoring ecological “functions” and “services” through remedial action (pp. 4–5). At the same time, the Directive contains a secondary intrinsic framing, particularly through its emphasis on *conservation* and long-term *ecological integrity*. The requirement that operators take preventive measures in cases of an “imminent threat of environmental damage” (p. 5), alongside references to the “long-term survival” of species and habitats (p. 4), indicating a *normative limit* beyond which damage is unacceptable. A relational dimension is also present but less dominant, particularly in provisions enabling civil society participation, where non-governmental organisations and affected parties are entitled to request action (p. 8), reflecting *participation* and shared *responsibility*. Overall, the prevailing value type is instrumental, albeit tempered

by intrinsic (preventive/threshold-based) elements. The Directive thus frames nature primarily as a repairable system of functions under human management, rather than as intrinsically valuable.

Green Deal-era

The European Green Deal (2019)

The Green Deal is a set of policy initiatives from the European Commission that aim at achieving climate neutrality in the EU by 2050. The policy document opens with strong intrinsic signalling, emphasising biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation as urgent in themselves (e.g. “one million...species...at risk of being lost”, p. 2). However, this intrinsic framing and measures to protect ecosystems is quickly subordinated to an instrumental *green growth* discourse, opening with a call to transform the economy and put society on a sustainable path (p. 2) and the belief that the policy must “maximise benefits for health, quality of life, resilience and competitiveness” (p. 3). The document positions the Green Deal as a “new growth strategy” aimed at a “competitive economy” (p. 2). Nature is primarily valued as natural capital and ecosystem service provider, reflecting the *economic asset* discursive tendency. This is evident in statements such as “ecosystems provide essential services such as food, fresh water and clean air” (p. 13). Frequent references to decarbonisation, carbon pricing, circular economy, and innovation reflect how environmental problems are framed as manageable through efficiency, markets, and technology. The *technosolutionist* discursive tendency is well presented: “New technologies, sustainable solutions and disruptive innovation are critical to achieve the objectives of the European Green Deal” (p. 18). Additionally, an anthropocentric *risk* discourse is already present from the onset of the document, as it states that human health and well-being needs to be protected against environment-related risks (p. 2), and as it frames environmental degradation as a “threat multiplier” affecting security and human well-being (p. 21). Relational elements

that point to a *responsibility* discursive tendency, such as how the Green Deal should serve future generations (p. 24) are only present at the very end of the policy text. Overall, the prevailing value of nature is instrumental.

The Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (2019)

The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 introduces a long-term framework to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems. The strategy exhibits a predominantly instrumental framing of nature, in which biodiversity is systematically articulated as a means to provide economic benefits and support human health, signalling the *economic asset* discursive tendency. Environmental protection is described as an “economic imperative” (p. 4). More specifically, the conservation of biodiversity is framed as having a significant impact on economic benefits, presented in numerical cost/benefit ratios (p. 1). Intact natural environments are viewed as providing comprehensive ecosystem services to human society, e.g., when it is claimed that “protecting and restoring biodiversity and well-functioning ecosystems is therefore key to boost our resilience and prevent the emergence and spread of future diseases” right at the start of the Strategy (p.1). In addition to this, intrinsic framings are present but often embedded within instrumental reasoning. Ecosystems such as forests and soils are occasionally described in terms that suggest intrinsic value, e.g., soil as “a habitat in its own right” hosting diverse life (p. 8), yet these descriptions are quickly coupled with their functional benefits for climate regulation, food production, or economic health. This indicates a hybrid framing where intrinsic value is acknowledged but subordinated to ecosystem functionality. Relational values appear comparatively weak and implicit. While references to the One Health approach and EU’s Urban Greening Platform (pp.12–13) suggest the recognition of human–nature interdependence, these are not extensively developed discursively. Overall, the dominant tendency is instrumental valuation, with nature primarily framed as an *economic asset*, while intrinsic values are conditional and relational values remain marginal.

The new Common Agricultural Policy 2023–2027 (2019-2023)

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is the agricultural policy of the European Union. For the period 2023–2027, the CAP is built around ten key objectives. In this analysis, we focus on Objective 4 (on agriculture and climate mitigation) as well as 6 (on biodiversity and farmed landscapes) and on the Summary document of the EC.

The CAP 2023–2027 documents exhibit a predominantly instrumental framing of nature, in which biodiversity and ecosystems are primarily valued for their functional contributions to agricultural productivity, while still incorporating some elements of *conservation*, *ecological integrity* and *stewardship*. The discursive tendency of *conservation* is present, e.g. when the summary mentions enabling biodiversity (p.5) and the “conservation and management of permanent grasslands” (p.6). There are traces of an *ecological integrity* discursive tendency, particularly in the explicit rejection of reductionist framings of biodiversity: “the issue of biodiversity cannot be reduced to landscapes and their features: it reaches well beyond that” (CAP Objective 6, p. 6). At the same time, relational elements of *stewardship* emerge in the emphasis on active human management (e.g. low-intensity grazing maintaining species richness), which frames farmers as ecological stewards (CAP Objective 6, p. 12) and in references where intensification is seen as coming at an environmental cost (CAP Objective 6, p. 12). However, overall, the CAP documents most explicitly show the *economic asset*, *green growth* and *technosolutionism* discursive tendency. This version of the CAP introduces eco-schemes to compensate farmers for taking environmental measures (Summary, p. 1). It is the assertion that “global agricultural production will need to increase, while at the same time keeping emissions under control” (CAP Objective 4, p. 13), embedding environmental protection within productivity imperatives, reflecting the *green growth* discursive tendency. In light of those instrumental discursive tendencies, trade-offs should be considered, not avoided: “Since productivity increases might lead to an intensification of agriculture, the potential negative

environmental impact and trade-offs should be carefully considered” (CAP Objective 4, p. 13). This is reinforced by *technosolutionist* approaches such as precision farming and nitrogen-fixing crops (CAP Objective 4, p. 13) and the bioeconomy (CAP Objective 4, p. 1), which position environmental challenges as manageable through innovation: “Specific efforts are planned to support more resource-efficient and knowledge-based agriculture through precision farming, cooperation and the exchange of knowledge on digital issues” (Summary, p. 11). It further introduces *risk* and *geopolitical asset* discursive tendencies, presenting a language of resilience, where nature is tied to food security in the context of external shocks (e.g. war-induced supply disruptions, Summary, p. 2) and where “some farming rules were temporarily relaxed to help produce more food” (Summary, p. 2). Overall, while intrinsic and relational values are present, the most dominant discursive tendencies are instrumental, particularly *green growth*, *economic asset* and *technosolutionism* discursive tendencies appear throughout the documents.

EU Climate Adaptation Strategy (2021)

The EU Climate Adaptation Strategy aims at making the EU climate-resilient. The strategy focuses strongly on instrumental valuations of nature, with the occasional more intrinsic framing and one single relational phrasing. There is a strong tendency towards *economic asset* discursive tendency at the beginning of the Strategy and throughout. For example, the document highlights potential and existing economic losses due to climate change (p. 1), as well as the “triple dividend’ of adaptation” (p. 2): avoiding losses, generating economic benefits, and providing social, environmental and cultural benefits. Job losses in climate-affected sectors are also referred to (p. 9). Furthermore, the document stresses the importance of ecosystem services (pp. 5, 12, 16), briefly distinguishing between services to people and to the environment (p. 17), and highlights the many benefits that are endangered by climate change and insufficient adaptive measures. Finally, the strategy briefly suggests considering the true cost of water and proposes introducing economic pricing measures as

a policy tool for valuing nature. Alongside this economic framing of nature, the document exhibits a strong tendency towards *risk* discourse, with references such as "a stark warning of the dangers of insufficient preparation", "increasing the likelihood of a best-case scenario", "frequency and severity of climate and weather extremes is increasing", and "climate change impacts are having far-reaching effects" (p. 1). These nature-related risks are addressed through the language of adaptation and resilience, for example, "we have to build a more resilient tomorrow" (p. 1), as well as *technosolutionist* discourse, for example, "stimulating innovation" (p. 2) and promoting "the use of the latest digital technologies" (p. 5) in order to reach environmental objectives. Beyond instrumental valuation, the general pursuit of protection, including in adaptation measures, can be deemed an intrinsic valuation of nature to a certain extent (p. 8), as can the reference to the One Health approach (p. 7), which is linked to a relational value of nature. However, these remain marginal throughout the document.

Post-Green Deal

Nature Restoration and amending Regulation (2024)

The Nature Restoration and amending Regulation requires Member States to adopt nature restoration measures. It is characterised by a dominant instrumental valuation of nature, articulated through a strong coupling of ecological, economic, and social benefits, while intrinsic and relational values are present but subordinated. Farmland birds, for instance, are framed primarily as "indicators of the health of agricultural ecosystems" (p. 10), instrumentalizing them. This hierarchy is further underscored by the passage stating that where food security and nature restoration conflict, food security can legally override restoration obligations (p. 41), indicating that anthropocentric priorities ultimately structure the valuation of nature. The most salient discursive tendency is nature as an *economic asset*. This is evident in recurring signalling

terms such as "ecosystem services", "natural capital", and cost-benefit reasoning, for instance where "the benefits of restoring degraded ecosystems... far outweigh the costs" (p. 3). This is embedded within a broader *green growth* narrative where restoration is linked to "economic and societal transformation, the creation of high-quality jobs and sustainable growth" (p. 3). Nature is consistently framed as performing functions for human wellbeing, e.g. carbon sinks, air and water filtering, cooling, food, pandemic barriers. This is further underlined by a narrative of *risk*, such as framing restoration of nature as an "insurance policy" ensuring long-term sustainability and resilience (p. 4). At the same time, intrinsic values are present in passages stressing the importance of long-term survival of those species (pp. 5–6). However, these intrinsic values are frequently re-integrated into instrumental reasoning (e.g. species as indicators of ecosystem health, p. 10). Relational values are comparatively thin but visible in passages recognising *interdependence*, such as references to "One Health" (p. 4), *participation* in referring to stakeholder engagement (p. 16), and *stewardship* in agroecological practices that sustain "landscape features" and long-term ecosystem functioning (p. 10). Yet, these passages remain largely justified through viewing nature as a service provider.

Clean Industrial Deal (2025)

The Clean Industrial Deal aims at decarbonisation for economic competitiveness of EU industries. The Deal is strongly characterised by instrumental values, with nature overwhelmingly framed through *green growth*, *economic asset*, *geopolitical asset*, and *technosolutionist* discursive tendencies, while intrinsic value is notably absent and relational value appears only marginally. The dominant discourse constructs nature as a functional input into industrial competitiveness and security, rather than as an entity with intrinsic worth. This is most clearly reflected in the coupling of environmental and economic objectives, e.g. the statement that circularity "creates a more sustainable industrial model that benefits the environment and enhances economic competitiveness" (p. 2), exemplifying a *green growth* narrative in

which decarbonisation and circularity are instrumental to economic expansion rather than ecological protection. References to the EU Emission Trading System (p. 7) and to carbon accounting (p. 8) point to an *economic asset* discursive tendency. Environmental problems are framed as manageable through innovation and efficiency improvements (e.g. clean tech, circularity), revealing the *technosolutionist* tendency in framing environmental problems. Nature is rendered measurable and manageable, reduced to carbon metrics, life-cycle assessments, and resource flows—rather than a complex ecological system. This aligns with the document’s implicit reduction of nature to two primary functions: a carbon sink and a source of raw materials, with minimal reference to broader ecosystem functions. Additionally, a *geopolitical asset* framing appears where natural resources and energy are tied to strategic autonomy, resilience, and security, e.g. the problematisation of fossil fuel import dependence (p. 2). Relational values are weak and largely confined to just transition language, such as ensuring that “every person, community, and business should benefit” (p. 20), but this is framed in socio-economic rather than ecological terms. Overall, the most dominant discursive tendency is instrumental *green growth* combined with *technosolutionism*, and the prevailing value of nature is instrumental, with intrinsic value entirely absent and relational value only superficially present.

Nature Credits Roadmap (2025)

The Nature Credits Roadmap aims at mobilising private investments into nature protection measures. The Roadmap is strongly characterised by an instrumental valuation of nature, with only marginal and subordinated relational elements and very limited intrinsic valuation. Throughout the document, nature is consistently framed through signalling terms associated with the economic asset discursive tendency, such as “competitiveness”, “value creation”, “ecosystem services”, “investment”. From the outset, nature is positioned as a functional input into human systems, e.g. “our strongest ally to support our livelihoods, health and prosperity” and “a crucial foundation for a competitive

and resilient economy” (p. 2). Nature credits are an explicit articulation of the commodification of nature, as they seek to translate ecosystems into tradable units that can be “registered, pooled, banked and transacted” (p. 5). While the document briefly acknowledges limitations of the instrumentalisation of nature, e.g. “ecosystem services remain difficult to monetise” and risks of “greenwashing” (p. 3), these concerns remain limited to problematizing implementation rather than questioning commodification itself. References to the bioeconomy (p. 1), suggest a *green growth* narrative. The concept of “nature-positive” further rearticulates conservation as a productive and investable activity, reinforcing this narrative. Additionally, *technosolutionist* language is pervasive, with repeated emphasis on “innovative tools”, and “metrics” indicating that environmental problems are framed primarily as challenges to be managed and optimised rather than ethically constrained. Relational values appear only in a subordinate, legitimising role. For instance, while references to “farmers, foresters... Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities” and their “roles as stewards” (p. 9) invoke discursive tendencies of *responsibility* and participation, these actors are primarily framed as participants in emerging markets. Intrinsic value is present but discursively not explicitly represented. Overall, the document is dominated by an instrumental valuation of nature, with relational elements instrumentalised and intrinsic value marginalised.

Simplifying for environmental sustainability (2025)

The Simplifying for sustainable competitiveness Omnibus outlines how the EU aims to reduce administrative burdens in sustainability reporting and streamline sustainability regulations to make them more efficient. The document is strongly characterised by an instrumental valuation of nature, with frequent references to nature as an *economic asset*. For example, it highlights that “19 out of 23 economic sectors ... [have] dependencies on nature” (p. 1) and frames nature loss as an economic risk, noting that “environmental degradation ... [causes] damage to the economy, infrastructure and financial stability” (p. 1). This is further reinforced by a clear *green growth* discursive

tendency, such as the claim that “a healthy planet and resilient economy go hand in hand” (p. 1) and that “competitiveness and sustainability are two sides of the same coin” (p. 1). Overall, the document is structured around the premise that environmental problems are fixable and optimisable, reflecting a distinctly *technosolutionist* approach. This is explicitly articulated in the statement that the simplification package “aims to ensure that the environmental goals of the European Union are achieved in more efficient, less costly and smarter ways” (p. 1). More broadly, the emphasis on increasing the efficiency of existing environmental policies, particularly by reducing “administrative burden” (e.g. p. 2,3) and streamlining time- and resource-intensive processes such as environmental assessments, further signals a *technosolutionist* discourse. Another prominent discursive tendency is the framing of nature as a *geopolitical asset*. While the omnibus largely reaffirms and builds upon existing (pre-Green Deal) environmental legislation, such as the Birds, Habitats, and Water Directives, by simplifying their implementation, it also reflects a geopolitical embedding of environmental policy. There is a stronger emphasis on strategic autonomy and the broader geoeconomic context. For instance, the introduction suggests that reducing the costs of achieving environmental goals should primarily contribute to the EU’s economy and strategic autonomy (p. 1), and states that “environmental protection must be secured in a way that enables Europe to rise effectively to the unprecedented geoeconomic, geopolitical and security challenges it faces” (p. 1). This indicates a strategic and geopolitical instrumentalisation of nature. By contrast, intrinsic values of nature are only weakly represented, as references to environmental protection are consistently subordinated to instrumental concerns. This is evident in formulations such as: “the protection of Europe’s environment is imperative for our resilience, prosperity and competitiveness”. (p. 1) Finally, relational values are also largely absent.

2. Overall changes throughout the phases

Overall, a shift in discursive tendencies can be discerned in the language used in EU environmental policy documents. Pre-Green Deal policies examined in this report place greater emphasis on protecting nature for its intrinsic value. In contrast, Green Deal-era policies shift the focus toward managing nature to support economic objectives. Post-Green Deal environmental policies go a step further by framing nature within a geopolitical context, highlighting its role in achieving strategic, security, and competitiveness goals. Early documents centre on discursive tendencies of *conservation*, *normative limits*, and *ecological integrity*. Green Deal-era texts intensify *economic asset*, *green growth*, *risk*, and *technosolutionist* framings. Post-Green Deal texts consolidate those instrumental tendencies while adding a much sharper *geopolitical asset* layer.

In view of the contrasting underlying normative assumptions of these tendencies, this is a considerable shift in the discursive tendencies present in the documents analysed here. However, one should take into account that these are developments that have spanned several decades. Further, intrinsic and relational valuations do not disappear, as earlier environmental policies remain in force, are being updated through amendments and new versions. Their importance is reiterated in newer policies building on these earlier ones. However, intrinsic values, and to a lesser extent relational ones, have a different function in the later phases of European environmental policy. Through time, they are increasingly framed as legitimising narratives or normative justification rather than the ultimate reason or decision-making principle behind the policies, constituting a different and more substantial change next to the change in tendencies merely being present in policy. Conversely, while instrumental and in particular economic framings of nature are present from the earliest policy documents analysed in this report, they start to appear in an increasing frequency in the Green Deal era and beyond, as the numerous

mentions of ecosystem services in the Green Deal era and Post-Green Deal era show.

Put differently, the dominant discursive shift is from valuing nature as an object of protection to valuing nature as a strategic resource within broader socio-economic and geopolitical projects, presented by a progressive reordering of value hierarchies, not a simple replacement of one discourse by another.

Pre-Green Deal

The Birds Directive, Habitats Directive, and much of the Water Framework Directive are anchored in a language of conservation, protection, prevention, maintenance, and restoration. The dominant discursive tendencies in this phase are *conservation*, *normative limits*, and *ecological integrity*, while instrumental reasoning is not completely absent in this phase. For instance, the Water Framework Directive still contains strong intrinsic signals, but already introduces cost recovery, proportionality, and the polluter-pays principle. As early as 2004 the Environmental Liability Directive goes further by reframing environmental harm in terms of measurable impairment, baseline condition, and remediation. So even before the Green Deal, one can already see the early institutionalisation of what Froese & Loft (2025) call a Green Economy pathway: Their analysis of the CAP shows that in this policy nature is framed in a way that “prioritises environmental goals alongside economic growth, often over-shadowing non-economic nature values” (p. 1)

Green Deal-era

In Schunz (2022)’s reading of EU environmental policy, during the Europe 2010-2020 period, sustainability becomes an “attribute to growth” supporting a jobs-and-growth agenda. Our policy selection captures that transition at the level of environmental policy language itself, because what changes in this phase is not

only the frequency of economic terms, but the pattern of justification. The imperative now is not just to protect nature, but to protect nature because this supports prosperity, jobs, and economic growth. In the Green Deal-era, instrumental values of nature become much more systematic, as the European Green Deal, Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, CAP 2023–2027, and Climate Adaptation Strategy all show strong recurrence of *green growth*, *economic asset*, *technosolutionism*, and *risk* discursive tendencies. This is aligned with the findings of the analysis by Eckert and Kovalevska (2021) who argue that the Green Deal repackages existing “green growth” narratives rather than transforming it. Nature is repeatedly articulated through ecosystem services, economic transformation, cost-benefit analysis, innovation, and efficiency. Even where intrinsic claims appear, they are often quickly folded back into utility-based reasoning. Schunz (2022) sees the Green Deal as a discursive break in which environmental sustainability becomes the organising principle of EU policy. Our analysis shows that, while the Green Deal moves the environment to the centre, this focus is largely mediated through instrumental discourse rather than a restoration of intrinsic valuation. This is in line with the discourse analysis of the CAP by Froese & Loft (2025) mentioned before, which further solidifies this finding: environmental protection is increasingly translated into costs, incentives, and managerial tools.

Our analysis does not discuss how key issues are discursively sidelined. While this is important as discursive change is not only about what increases (e.g. economic language) but also about what disappears (e.g. references to limits to growth), our findings here are supported by the discourse analysis of the Green Deal by Eckert and Kovalevska (2021). They argue that in foregrounding technological innovation and market-based solutions, the discourse sidelines more transformative alternatives, such as degrowth or absolute reductions in resource use, thus not only subordinating intrinsic values but actively obscuring structural contradictions between economic growth and ecological limits.

Post-Green Deal

In this last phase, the instrumental discursive tendencies intensify, while a new and significant discursive tendency emerges: the framing of nature as a *geopolitical asset*. Again, and in line with the reasoning of Schunz (2022) that certain 'crises' shape the perspective from which policy-makers frame policies, Froese & Loft (2025) also refer in this phase to the formative moments of COVID-19 and the war against Ukraine that lead to security-oriented priorities in policies. Our analysis echoes this, showing that in this later phase of EU environmental policies, the value of nature is increasingly tied to industrial independence, strategic autonomy, energy security, and the EU's position in an unstable world. Nature is framed not only as economically valuable, but as strategically necessary. The analysis of the Nature Restoration and amending Regulation by Fleckenstein et al. (2025) reaffirms and further illustrates that intrinsic conservation aims persist in recent EU environmental policy, but are increasingly negotiated and partially weakened through competing economic and strategic storylines, i.e. instrumental justifications such as cost/benefit reasoning, feasibility, production restrictions, food security, and securing greater flexibility to protect economic interests.

Discussion

The analysis presented in this report shows that changes in EU environmental policy discourse are not characterised by a simple replacement of one valuation of nature by another, but by different justifications. While intrinsic values serve as a primary rationale in earlier environmental policies, this value is increasingly embedded within and subordinated to broader instrumental framings. This is aligned with scholarship arguing that EU environmental governance increasingly frames nature through economic and functional reasoning, particularly via ecosystem services and natural capital approaches and that different value types coexist, but are selectively mobilised within governance frameworks (Raymond et al., 2025). While this is a development that can be traced back to as early as 2004, earlier directives such as the Birds and Habitats Directives remain in force and continue to anchor intrinsic and conservation-oriented language within the EU policy framework. The Green Deal has been described as a paradigm shift in the academic debate (Schunz 2022), however our analysis shows that the foundations for these discursive tendencies were already laid at an earlier stage. So, while the Green Deal indeed has an effect in the discursive shifts considered, these did not originate with the implementation of the Green Deal.

An important factor in this dynamic is the force of policy integration enhanced and expanded by the Green Deal. In the Green Deal era, policy integration elevated environmental policy to a central position within the EU's broader economic and political agenda. Environmental objectives were no longer confined to a distinct policy domain but were explicitly linked to economic growth and competitiveness. This integration led to subordinating the intrinsic and relational justifications of protecting nature to instrumental ones, as nature

became increasingly articulated in ways that supported, rather than constrained, these instrumental objectives. As for the relational values, Turnhout et al. (2015) further argue that although the norm of participation was increasingly evoked to address the needs of stakeholders in EU environmental policies, the norm of (cost-)effectiveness continued to dominate the construction of legitimacy, aligning with our findings. So, on the one hand, embedding environmental policy within broader strategies such as the European Green Deal enhances its political salience and increases its reach to other policy domains. On the other hand, it appears to restructure the hierarchy of values, making environmental protection contingent upon its contribution to economic prosperity, resilience, and, more recently, geopolitical stability. The emergence of geopolitical asset framing in the post-Green Deal phase marks a further development of this trajectory and shows an intensification of instrumentalisation. Potentially, if geopolitical tensions and challenges increase, this could give rise to further occasions for shifts of intrinsic valuation discursive tendencies towards more instrumental types, considering the increase in mentions of geopolitical events such as the Russian invasion in Ukraine, as we found in analysing the documents.

The analysis thus raises questions on how policy integration and value plurality are related. On the one hand, as environmental policy becomes increasingly integrated into economic and geopolitical agendas, the use of instrumental language may be further intensified, since policies must be justified within these dominant frameworks, e.g. the Green Deal. On the other hand, when policies are developed within their own distinct framing, this can lead to policy fragmentation, potentially decreasing effectiveness, an issue highlighted by

Elomina and Pülzl (2021). They argue that this can be addressed by increasing policymakers' awareness of different discursive tendencies in framing the value of nature across policy domains, thereby enhancing coordination and reducing fragmentation. Our findings suggest that while policies developed within broader strategic frameworks may achieve greater political reach, they also appear more likely to subordinate intrinsic values to instrumental values. Potentially, this could be a reason to object to excessive policy integration. However, as our analysis is based on a selection of policy documents and does not focus on implementation outcomes, it cannot establish causal relationships between discursive shifts and policy effectiveness.

To conclude, while the discursive changes date back to the early 2000s and hence predate the establishment of the Green Deal, the integrative force of the Deal seems to have catalysed the instrumentalisation or the subordination of more intrinsic valuations. Hence, one perspective to consider in further reflection would be to balance the benefits involved in more comprehensive and integrated regulatory practice — as mentioned by Schunz (2022) — with the apparent subordination of intrinsic values of nature to more instrumental types of valuation.

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